

USE OF INNOVATIVE METHODS IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION CLASSES

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KEYWORDS

lesson planning,
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ABSTRACT

The teacher sets goals for the lesson, makes decisions, plans, organizes the lesson process, monitors its progress and results, and changes the content as needed.

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In physical education classes in secondary schools, the teacher sets the purpose of the lesson, makes decisions, plans the lesson, organizes the lesson process, monitors its progress and results, changes the content, if necessary, the issue of introduction and use of modern teaching methods in the educational process remains relevant.

All didactic and technical information that the teacher needs before the lesson prepare the tools and ensure that the lesson is organized effectively.

The teacher's organizational role is evident before, during, and after class. The teacher sets goals, makes decisions, plans, organizes the lesson process, monitors its progress and results, and changes the content as needed.

After completing all the organizational work, the teacher should determine the effectiveness of the lesson and analyze the results, as well as study the impressions of students through practical exercises, which will help to determine the direction of further pedagogical activity.

Not only is the teacher fully aware of the nature of the interactive methods planned to be used in the process of organizing small research and innovative activities as a manager, but also the organizational and methodological organization of the lesson, control over student activities, it is important to be able to quickly sense that an accident or error has occurred, to manage problem situations correctly, and to have the ability to make certain corrections throughout the lesson. His knowledge of the specific objectives of the course stages allows for a coherent, continuous and creative organization of the course.

The effectiveness of the organization of physical education classes with the help of modern technology is directly related to the following conditions:

- high visibility of the studied movements;
- Supervise students' movements and strengthen their skills during the lesson;
- Periodically update the study activities and enrich them with new information go;
- The teacher has a deep knowledge, skills and competencies in the theory and teaching methods of their subject, the specific mental and physical characteristics of students;
- be able to plan each lesson in an innovative and pedagogical way; -cultivate high moral and spiritual qualities in students;
- comply with the requirements of the law on the rights and protection of students;
- be creative and inquisitive to increase students' knowledge and enable them to apply their knowledge in practice;
- be able to organize each lesson to focus on life skills;
- be able to organize teaching methods in different ways, taking into account the interests and abilities of students;
- be able to effectively organize each lesson;

The course requires the teacher to direct the activities of all small groups, to provide assistance in case of need, as well as to provide psychological support, to monitor the analysis of the content of the work. In addition, the teacher should prepare the necessary

teaching aids for the teaching process.

In conclusion, we hope that the effective implementation of the above tasks in the classroom will help to increase the effectiveness of the lessons.

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